

Methods of Nano Zinc Oxide Synthesis and its Characterization: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Metal oxides have achieved much attention due to their unique properties and potential application in the field of nanomaterials. Among them zinc oxide (ZnO) nanomaterials are of immense importance owing to their unique electrical, optical and magnetic properties, broadening their applications in the field of material science and industrial applications. This review primarily aims to describe the recent developed methodologies for the synthesis and characterization of ZnO nanomaterials.

KEYWORDS: Metal oxide, nanomaterial, synthesis

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1. INTRODUCTION

The whole thing in the world is made up of atoms and molecules. The fundamental units of a matter have been of more attention to researchers since the beginning.¹ By examining the atomic properties of a substance, we gain a deeper understanding of its properties and can gain a better understanding of the material. In addition, small or major modifications in certain materials can have a significant impact on their characteristics. This significant change can be observed at the nanoscale.² The size of a particle is reduced to a few nanometres, resulting in a significant alteration in its optical, physical, electrical, mechanical, and chemical properties. This change occurs because of the increase in surface area to volume ratio with at least one dimension in nanometres. The new properties can make the material more efficient than its bulk form. Nanoparticles have sizes ranging from 1 nm to 100 nm. When materials are reduced in size, typically to the nanometer scale, a significant and remarkable change occurs in their bulk properties. The unique physical, chemical, optical, electrical, catalytic, and magnetic properties of nanoparticles, which differ from both bulk materials and individual atoms or

molecules, can be attributed to either the surface effect or the quantum-size effect resulting from quantum-mechanical principles.

Metal and metal oxide nanoparticles are widely used as catalysts in various chemical reactions, biomedical application such as drug delivery, imaging, and therapy.^{3,4} Metal and metal oxide nanoparticles also used as a gas sensors, biosensors, and environmental monitoring devices and storage device like batteries, supercapacitors and fuel cells and they are employed for the removal of pollutants from air and water.⁵⁻⁷

Metallic oxides have attracted wide attention due to their unique properties and potential application in nano device fabrication. Among different metal oxides, zinc oxides, owing to wide range band gap of 3.3 eV at 300 K and large excitonic binding energy of 60 meV have made it important for scientific as well as industrial applications.⁸⁻¹¹ Reduction in size to nano scale, novel electrical, mechanical, chemical and optical properties are introduced to ZnO nanomaterials due to surface and quantum confinement effect.¹² Some basic physical and chemical properties of ZnO is summarized herewith

(Table 1). These unique properties give ZnO several advantages as active material in the usage of gas sensors, solar cells, field effect transistors, light emitting devices.¹³⁻¹⁶ Zinc oxide nanoparticles are used in various applications like electronics, medicinal fields, antibacterial textiles¹⁷, antibacterial and antifungal agents when integrated into plastics

and paints.¹⁸ The optical, electrical, and magnetic characteristics of ZnO nanostructures are strongly dependent to their structural morphology. Therefore, there has been a strong interest in the synthesis of ZnO nanostructures with well-controlled size and shape.

Table 1: Basic physical & Chemical Properties of zinc oxide

Property	Description
Appearance	Zinc oxide typically appears as a white powder, although it can also be found in other forms such as crystals or granules depending on how it is manufactured.
Molecular weight	81.37 g/mol
Melting Point	The melting point of zinc oxide is relatively high, around 1975°C (3587°F).
Boiling Point	Zinc oxide has a very high boiling point, around 2360°C (4280°F),
Density	The density of zinc oxide varies depending on its form, but typically ranges from about 5.47 to 5.61 grams per cubic centimetre.
Solubility	Zinc oxide is insoluble in water, meaning it does not dissolve in water. However, it is soluble in acidic or alkaline solutions
Crystal Structure	wurtzite
Lattice Constant	a = b=3.25 Å, c = 5.2 Å
Refractive Index	The refractive index of zinc oxide varies from about 1.9 to 2.0.
Band gap energy	3.4 eV
Excitation binding energy	60 eV

2. Synthesis and characterization of ZnO nanoparticles

The ZnO nano particle can be synthesized following two approaches i.e top down approaches and. bottom up approaches. The bottom up approaches has some advantages over top down approaches. In bottom up approaches the nano particles obtained with less crystal defect, narrow size distribution and of high purity and homogeneity. Some bottom up methods for ZnO synthesis, such as co-precipitation method, solvo-thermal synthesis, sol-gel process, electrochemical deposition and micro-emulsions make it possible to obtain products with particles, differing in shape, size and spatial structure. Some bottom up approaches for synthesizing ZnO nano particle have been discussed herewith.

2.1. Co-precipitation method: Co-precipitation is the simultaneous precipitation of more than one compound from a solution. It is the most convenient inexpensive technique for the preparation of NPs. In this method, metal precipitates in the form of hydroxide from a salt precursor in the presence of a base in a solvent.

Ghorbani *et al.* synthesized ZnO nanoparticles by co-precipitation method using zinc nitrate as a precursor in aqueous solution. UV-vis spectroscopy confirmed the formation of ZnO nanoparticles in the solution. Using dynamic light scattering (DLS) technique they determined the average size of synthesized nanoparticle of 30 nm. The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) study showed and confirmed the formation of nano-sized ZnO particles. [Table 2, Entry 1].

Purwaningsih *et al.* synthesized spherical nano zinc by co-precipitation method using zinc acetate dehydrate as a precursor in various pH ranging from 8 to 10. The purity, microstructure, chemical group analysis, morphology of the prepared ZnO powder was studied by XRD, FTIR, SEM & EDX respectively. The XRD & EDX analysis confirmed the synthesis of nano ZnO with high purity & Rietveld refinement of XRD data showed that ZnO crystallizes in the wurtzite structure. The obtained powder was nano-sized particles with the average crystallite size about 17.9 ± 2.1 nm synthesized with pH of 9.5, at 85°C, and stirring time of 6 h. The SEM results have visualized the morphology of ZnO nanoparticles with spherical-like shape [Entry 2].

Adam *et al.* were synthesized ZnO NPs from aqueous zinc acetate dehydrate solution by the low temperature co-precipitation method. The X-ray diffraction analysis confirmed the presence of a hexagonal wurtzite structure in prepared samples, with no observable impurity phases. The average size of the nanoparticles estimated from SEM graph was found to be ~140 nm in diameter [Entry 3].

Ahamed *et al.* were synthesized ZnO nanoparticles via co-precipitation method using zinc nitrate aqueous solution. The synthesized particles were characterized by XRD, HRTEM, EDX and UV-visible spectroscopy.

The X-ray diffraction study revealed that the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles have wurtzite structure and the particle size varies from 35 to 40 nm. From HRTEM they found that the surface morphology of ZnO nanoparticle is spherical. The UV-Visible spectrum of the nanoparticles showed a red shift compared to that of the bulk sample [Entry 4].

2.2. Sol-gel method: Sol-gel deposition is a method of thin film deposition that involves the conversion of a precursor solution into a solid gel which is then deposited on a substrate to form a thin film. The process involves several steps, including hydrolysis, condensation, gelation, aging, and densification.

During the process, a solution of metal alkoxides or other precursor compounds is prepared and then hydrolyzed to form a colloidal suspension of metal oxide particles. This suspension is then spin-coated or dip-coated onto a substrate, where it is dried and heated to form a thin film.

Hasnidawani *et al.* reported the synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles via sol-gel method using Zinc acetate dehydrate as a precursor and ethanol as a solvent. The synthesized nano ZnO was characterized by using XRD, EDX, FESEM, and nano-particles analyser. EDX analysis confirmed the synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles with good purity. FESEM micrographs showed that synthesized ZnO has a rod-like structure. The particle size of synthesized ZnO powder is about 84.98 nm using nano-particle analyser. The XRD investigation also confirmed the synthesis of ZnO nano-powder with good crystallinity [Entry 5].

Benhebal *et al.* carried out the formation of powder ZnO by sol-gel method using zinc acetate dihydrate as precursor and ethanol as solvent. The as prepared ZnO was characterized by using nitrogen adsorption isotherms, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and UV-Vis spectroscopy. Photocatalytic activity of catalyst was evaluated by measuring the photo-degradation of phenol and benzoic acid. The XRD analysis exhibited that the nanoparticles have the hexagonal wurtzite structure and the diameter of crystallite size of synthesized ZnO powder was 20 nm. SEM analysis also confirmed the formation spherically shaped ZnO nano particles with uniform distribution [Entry 6].

Savi *et al.* synthesized and characterized ZnO nanoparticles by sol-gel technique using $ZnCl_2$ and $Zn(NO_3)_2$ as precursors. The characterization was performed by using XRD, UV-Vis, and HR-TEM techniques. The XRD & HRTEM analysis exhibited crystallite structure, size ranging between 20 and 40 nm. UV-Vis spectrometry results revealed that the band gap energy, as indicated by the absorbance at 300 nm, varied depending on the precursor employed [Entry 7].

Singh *et al.* synthesized ZnO nanoparticles via sol-gel method using zinc acetate di-hydrate [$Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$] as a precursor and ethanol as a solvent. XRD, SEM, and TEM techniques characterized the as-prepared ZnO nanoparticles. The study revealed successful synthesis of rod-like ZnO structures via the sol-gel method, with an average nano-size range between 81.28 nm to 84.98 nm using Scherrer's equation, and 100-200 nm as observed through SEM measurement for ZnO nano particles dried at 800°C. The resulting ZnO nano-powder was found to exhibit good crystallinity [Entry 8].

Abdullah *et al.* carried out the synthesis of zinc oxide with less than 50 nm average grain size by a sol-gel method and the powder shapes were almost uniform prepared by mixing a methanol solution and zinc acetate dehydrate and adding ammonia NH_4OH to adjust pH value of the solution between 9 and 11. The XRD analysis exhibited that the nanoparticles have the hexagonal wurtzite structure and an average particle size of 20 nm has been attained. Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) showed a homogeneous distribution of nanoparticles with an average size of 22 nm, which agrees with XRD results [Entry 9].

2.3. Solvothermal method: The solvothermal method is a straightforward and scalable process that is based on mixing all the precursors with ligands in a high boiling solvent inside a sealed stainless vessel. Then, the reaction is conducted increasing the temperature above the boiling point of the solvent in a lab autoclave and kept in these conditions during the desired time. This strategy provides a homogeneous and fast phase of heating up, a fine controllable size, and a reproducible large-scale procedure.

Fernandez *et al.* demonstrated a simple solvothermal method for synthesizing ZnO nanoparticles using zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$), zinc acetate dehydrate ($Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$), zinc acetylacetonate hydrate ($Zn(C_5H_7O_2)_2 \cdot xH_2O$) and silver nitrate ($AgNO_3$) as precursors. The obtained materials were characterized by XRD, SEM, HR-TEM, UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS), and Raman spectroscopy (RS). XRD results showed that all major peaks are indexed to the hexagonal wurtzite-type

structure. The EDS spectra reinforced the high purity of the synthesized nanoparticles and were correlated with the previous results obtained from the XRD analysis [Entry 10].

Wee *et al.* synthesized zinc Oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) with less than 10 nm size via solvothermal method using zinc acetate dihydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) as a precursor and absolute ethanol as solvent. The formation of as prepared ZnO nanoparticles were confirmed through various characterization techniques such as XRD, TEM, FT-IR, and UV-vis spectroscopy. XRD analysis revealed a wurtzite crystalline structure, while TEM showed sizes of less than 10 nm for the nanoparticles. BET analysis indicated a high surface area congruent with TEM results. TEM-EDX confirmed the purity of the nanoparticles, showing a high composition of Zn and O elements. FT-IR and UV-vis spectroscopy demonstrated absorbance spectra indicative of ZnO nanoparticles. Thus, solvothermal synthesis emerged as a promising method for high-quality ZnO nanoparticle production. This study also suggested a potentially efficient approach for achieving smaller particle sizes within shorter synthesis duration [Entry 11].

2.4. Microemulsion method: Microemulsion polymerization is a complex heterogeneous process where transport of monomers, free radicals and other species (such as chain transfer agent, co-surfactant and inhibitors) between the aqueous and organic phases takes place.

Li *et al.* were prepared ZnO nanostructures with different morphologies and optical properties by a simple microemulsion process by using zinc nitrate solution as a precursor. The samples were characterized by TEM, XRD, FTIR, and TG-DTA analysis. The XRD spectra depicted that the ZnO crystal has a hexagonal wurtzite structure. Needle-like, columnar and spherical ZnO samples were synthesized respectively with the increase of concentration in zinc nitrate solution. TEM images and thermogravimetric analysis revealed that the microemulsion interface and the PEG400 agent have a synergistic effect on the morphology and crystalline size transition of ZnO nanostructures. The optical properties of the samples were investigated by measuring the UV-Vis absorbance spectra at room temperature. All the samples exhibited strong UV absorption at around 365 nm [Entry 12].

Yıldırım *et al.* were prepared ZnO nanostructures by a simple microemulsion process by using zinc acetate dihydrate as a precursor. The formation of ZnO nanoparticles was achieved by calcination of premature zinc glycerolate microemulsion product in air at 300, 400 and 500 °C. The crystal structure and the morphology of the ZnO nanoparticles were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Average crystallite size estimated from the XRD results ranging from 16.4-26.8 nm and average particle size as determined from SEM examinations for the ZnO nanoparticles calcined at different temperatures are 15-24 nm [Entry 13].

2.5. Electrochemical deposition: Electrochemical deposition is a process of depositing a thin layer of material on a conductive substrate through an electrochemical reaction. The process involves the use of an electrolytic cell where the substrate acts as the cathode and the anode is made of the material to be deposited. When a potential is applied between the anode and the cathode, the material from the anode gets oxidized and ions are transported through the electrolyte to the cathode. Here, the ions are reduced and deposited as a thin layer on the substrate.

Mah *et al.* synthesized ZnO with cube-like nanostructures that have been fabricated on tin-doped indium oxide (ITO) coated glass substrates via the electrochemical deposition method. The XRD measurement showed that the as-deposited nanostructures are converted from amorphous to hexagonal wurtzite ZnO phase after heat treatment at 600 °C for 3 hours. FESEM images observed that the average size of the cube-like nano ZnO materials is decreased from 207 nm to 102 nm with increasing electrolytes concentration. The XRD measurement showed that the as-deposited nanostructures are converted from amorphous to hexagonal wurtzite ZnO phase after heat treatment at 600 °C for 3 hours [Entry 14].

Aranda *et al.* investigated the synthesis and characterization of zinc oxide (ZnO) nanorods grown on zinc oxide and silver nanoparticle seeds. Zinc oxide seeds were electrodeposited onto fluorine-doped tin oxide glass and heat-treated, followed by the deposition of silver nanoparticles and another heat treatment. SEM images revealed nanosheets transforming into nanoparticles. ZnO nanorods grown on Ag/ZnO seeds were circular, while those on ZnO seeds were hexagonal. X-ray diffraction confirmed that the as deposited ZnO nano materials have a Wurtzite structure. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy detected elemental silver and silver oxide on silver nanoparticles and two types of oxygen [Entry 15].

Costovici *et al.* demonstrate the electrochemical synthesis of ZnO nanopowders by anodically dissolving a zinc electrode in either choline chloride-ethylene glycol or choline chloride-urea eutectic mixtures, along with hydrogen peroxide. The samples were characterized by using XRD, SEM, and EDX. XRD analysis peaks corresponding to the hexagonal wurtzite structure. SEM images revealed nanoparticles with an almost spherical shape and crystallite sizes ranging from approximately 15 to 31 nm, closely matching calculated values from XRD patterns. EDX spectra confirmed the slightly higher oxygen presence compared to zinc in the ZnO nanopowder [Entry 16].

Harden *et al.* synthesized bi-structured zinc oxide (ZnO) films onto ITO glass using a fixed cathodic voltage of -2.2 V and a reaction time of 90 minutes by electrochemical method. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis revealed the polycrystalline nature of the films. SEM images revealed the bi-structural characteristics of the ZnO, with dense hexagonal particles forming the bottom layer and plate-shaped structures growing on top of this base layer [Entry 17].

Haspulat-taymaz *et al.* synthesized zinc oxide (ZnO) and Ag-deposited ZnO (ZnO@Ag) core-shell nanorods electrochemically on an indium tin oxide-coated glass (ITO) substrate for the first time, without any organic surfactants or high annealing temperature. The nanorod films were synthesized using a two-step procedure. Firstly, ZnO nanorods were electrodeposited at low temperatures. In the second step, in situ electrochemical etching of the deposited ZnO nanorods was carried out. The strong and sharp peaks seen on the XRD patterns confirmed that the prepared samples have a complete crystalline structure. The SEM images showed that thin films have rough surfaces and consist of compact, uniform, and nanorod arrays. The obtained nanorod arrays produced on ITO substrate in the first-step electrodeposition were mainly 160–110 nm. AFM images also confirmed that the ZnO and ZnO@Ag films were nanorod arrays in diameter [Entry 18].

Table 2: Summary of Synthetic methods and characterization of nano zinc oxide

Entry	Methods	Zinc Precursor	Solvent	Reaction condition	Characterization techniques	Morphology (Size & Shape)	References
1.	Co-precipitation	Zinc nitrate	Aqueous	Room temperature, vigorous stirring,, calcined at 500 °C in air atmosphere for 3 h	UV-Visible spectroscopy, TEM &DLS	The size range of the generated ZnO powder was approximately 20–40 nm.	19
2.		Zinc acetate dihydrate	H ₂ O	Stirred continuously and controlled at 85 °C for 6h, pH= 8-10	SEM, XRD, EDX & FT-IR	Spherical, average crystallite size about 17.9 ± 2.1 nm	20
3.		Zinc acetate dihydrate	H ₂ O	Stirred at 750 rpm for 2 h, Temp=60°C	XRD, SEM	Hexagonal wurtzite, The average size of the nanoparticles ~140 nm in diameter	21
4.		Zn(NO ₃) ₂	H ₂ O	Time=2h, Temp=60°C	XRD, HRTEM & EDAX	The average crystallite size =39 nm, spherical, average size in the range of 35-40 nm(TEM)	22

5.	Sol-gel	Zinc acetate dihydrate	H ₂ O	The solutions were stirred with a constant stirring for about five minutes each	XRD, EDX, FESEM	Rod-like, The average crystallite size within 81.28nm to 84.98nm.	23
6.	Sol-gel	Zinc acetate dihydrate	Ethanol	Temp= 50°C Time= 60 min	XRD, TEM & SEM	Hexagonal wurtzite, The diameter of crystallite size = 20 nm.	24
7.		ZnCl ₂ , Zn(NO ₃) ₂	H ₂ O	Temp=50°C and 90°C, Time= 60 and 30 min	XRD, HRTEM,UV-Vis	Wurtzite structure, Crystallite size between 20 and 40 nm (HR-TEM and XRD)	25
8.		Zinc acetate dihydrate	Ethanol	Room Temperature, Stirred ultrasonically for 60 min.	XRD, SEM, TEM	Hexagonal structure, average Diameter= 20nm, the average nano-size=100-200nm	26
9.		Zinc acetate dihydrate	Methanol	Temp=80°C, Stirred for 2h	XRD, AFM	Hexagonal wurtzite, The average particle size was about 12-30 nm.	27
10.		Zinc nitrate	Ethanol	Temp=200°C, Time= 3h	XRD, SEM, HRTEM, UV-Vis & Raman spectroscopy	Hexagonal wurtzite	28
11.	Solvo-thermal	Zinc acetate dihydrate (Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·2H ₂ O)	Ethanol	Temp=60°C, Time= 3h	XRD, TEM, EDX, FT-IR & , UV-Vis	Wurtzite, crystalline size =10.08 nm (XRD), & 7.4 ±1.2nm. (TEM)	29

12.	Microemulsion	Zn(NO ₃) ₂		Time=15 h, Temp=140 °C;	TEM, XRD, FTIR, and TG-DTA	hexagonal (wurtzite) particles morphology: needle (Length: 150– 200 nm, Diameter: ~55 nm), nanocolumns (Length: 80–100 nm, Diameter: 50- 80 nm), spherical (~45 nm)	30
13.		Zinc acetate	Methanol	Time=24 h, temperature= 60–70 °C;	XRD, SEM	Hexagonal wurtzite structure, spherical shape (15-24 nm)	31
14.	Electrochemical Deposition	Zinc Chloride	H ₂ O	Temperature= 90 °C, Voltage=8 volts	XRD, FESEM, & EDX	Hexagonal Wurtzite	32
15.		Zinc acetate dihydrate	H ₂ O	Potential=-1.5 V & -0.5 V, Temperature=70 °C	XRD, SEM UV- Vis, cyclic voltammetry	Wurtzite-type, Size of the nanorods= 50nm	33
16.		Zinc acetate dihydrate	Choline chloride- ethylene glycol	Potential= (0-60 V), Current densities= 15 - 50 mA cm ⁻² , Temperature= 20-30 °C, Time= 3- 5 h.	XRD, SEM, EDX	Spherical shape, 15-31 nm (SEM), hexagonal wurtzite structure, 12- 18 nm (XRD)	34
17.		ZnCl ₂	Aqueous	Voltage = -2.2 V, Temp=80°C, time =90 min	SEM, XRD, EDX, photoluminescence (PL) spectrum	Hexagonal (wurtzite), average grain size = 530 ± 20 nm.	35
18.	Electrochemical Deposition	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Aqueous	Potential=-1.1 V, Temp= 80 °C, Time= 30 min under O ₂ atmosphere, potential= 1.45 V, Temp= 80 °C.	XRD,AFM, SEM, FTIR, EDX, UV- visible diffuse absorption spectra and photoluminescence spectroscopy (PL)	Hexagonal wurtzite, 160– 110 nm	36

3. Conclusion

Zinc oxide nanoparticles have widespread applications in diverse fields including biomedical applications due to their unique physical and chemical characteristics. Their exact physical and chemical behaviour are based on different methods used to synthesize them. Some synthetic methods with their characterization has been illustrated herewith. This illustration will surely help to develop new synthetic methodologies for ZnO nanomaterials.

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